

1 Control of the imprinting machinery by wild-type and mutant NOD2.

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7 We demonstrate here that NOD2 has the ability to control expression of molecules that function in the
8 endogenous Xist-associated imprinting system which changes substantially in quality in the presence of
9 the Crohn's Disease associated variant L1007fsinsC. The nuclear effector DZIP1L lied under weak control
10 of wild-type human NOD2 in a heterologous system. In primary monocytes from humans with Crohn's
11 Disease whose genomes contained a mutation in NOD2, however, DZIP1L was strongly activated,
12 indicating that NOD2 mutation resulted in DZIP1L engagement. Importantly, while cells expressing
13 wild-type NOD2 repressed DZIP3, expression of a NOD2 CD mutation in a heterologous system resulted
14 instead in weak activation of DZIP3. NOD2 has the ability to control expression of molecules that function
15 in the endogenous Xist-associated imprinting system, including molecules of the DZIP family, and this
16 changes substantially in quality in the presence of the Crohn's Disease associated variant L1007fsinsC.
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